

Problem (QUBO Graph)

Crossbar Matrix (W)

Energy Relaxation

Attractor Solution

RPU Platform Resonant Processing Unit

Architecture of a Stable Neuromorphic Processor

Description

RPU (Resonant Processing Unit) is a processor architecture based on nonlinear dynamical systems and adaptive synchronization.

Unlike conventional digital processors, computation is performed through the **natural evolution** of a controlled dynamical system toward a stable equilibrium state. The equilibrium state represents the final result of the computation.

Key Advantages:

- **High Computational Efficiency:** Leveraging physical convergence laws.
- **Low Energy Consumption:** Minimal energy state as a target.
- **Stable Operating Regimes:** Mathematically guaranteed robustness.
- **Predictable System Behavior:** Deterministic outcomes without "black box" uncertainty.

The architecture is designed for solving complex optimization problems and modeling high-dimensional physical and dynamical systems.

Operating Principle

The processor operates as a controlled nonlinear dynamical system that converges toward a **stable equilibrium**.

1. **Input:** Signals define the system's initial configuration and energy landscape.
2. **Process:** The system evolves naturally toward its lowest energy state.
3. **Output:** The resulting equilibrium state corresponds to the computed solution.

The mathematical structure (based on the *Structural No-Oscillation Theorem*) guarantees convergence and suppresses parasitic oscillations, enabling **deterministic and reliable** operation.

Application Areas

- **Optimization Problems:** Combinatorial and global optimization.
- **Complex System Modeling:** Weather, fluid dynamics, and N-body systems.
- **Signal Processing:** Real-time noise reduction and pattern recognition.
- **Scientific Computing:** Fast partition function calculations (5D mapping).
- **Physical Simulations:** Molecular and structural dynamics.
- **Neuromorphic Computing:** Brain-inspired, energy-efficient AI hardware.

System Architecture Overview

The RPU-1 architecture implements adaptive synchronization using a memristive crossbar fabric with programmable coupling and hardware stabilization loops.

RPU - 1 System Architecture

MEMRISTIVE CROSSBAR WITH PROGRAMMABLE LATERAL COUPLING

CALIBRATION & INITIALIZATION SYSTEM

Structural No-Oscillation Theorem

for Adaptive Kuramoto Systems with Cubic Saturation

Nonlinear Dynamical Systems • Control Theory • Neuromorphic Engineering

Theorem Overview

The RPU processor is governed by a nonlinear dynamical system controlling:

- Ψ : synchronization parameter
- Q : adaptive coupling

Reliable hardware operation requires the absolute absence of unstable oscillatory regimes.

The Structural No-Oscillation Theorem guarantees that oscillatory attractors are excluded from the model.

Mathematical Model

Processor dynamics are defined by the system:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\Psi} = \left(\frac{Q}{2} - \Delta\right)\Psi - c\Psi^3 \\ \dot{Q} = \frac{1}{\tau}(K_0 + \alpha\Psi - Q) \end{cases}$$

Parameters:

- Δ — dissipation | c — nonlinear saturation
- τ — relaxation time | K_0 — baseline excitation | α — coupling coefficient

Core Mathematical Properties

Boundary Invariance

The line $\Psi = 0$ is invariant. Trajectories cannot cross this boundary, and no periodic orbits can exist on it.

Global Dissipativity

Cubic saturation and adaptive relaxation ensure that all trajectories enter a compact region of state space. The system is structurally bounded.

Stable Equilibrium

The system converges to either a **trivial state** ($\Psi \approx 0$) or a **synchronized equilibrium** ($\Psi > 0$), which is asymptotically stable and represents reliable processor operation.

Exclusion of Oscillations

Using the **Bendixson–Dulac criterion**, we prove that periodic orbits and limit cycles are excluded:

$$\nabla \cdot (BF) < 0$$

in the admissible region. **Oscillatory attractors cannot exist.**

THE THEOREM

"For all admissible parameter values, trajectories remain bounded, periodic orbits do not exist, and the system converges globally to stable equilibrium states."

Engineering Significance

This theorem provides the mathematical foundation for:

- **Deterministic convergence:** Guaranteed results in real-time.
- **Oscillation suppression:** No parasitic hardware instability.
- **Predictable behavior:** Reliable performance in safety-critical systems.

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THE THEOREM

"For all admissible parameter values, trajectories remain bounded, periodic orbits do not exist, and the system converges globally to stable equilibrium states."

All figures present numerical simulations of the proposed dynamical model, confirming the theoretical results.

Attractor-Based Semantics

A Minimal Dynamical Model of Semantic States

Fundamental Hypothesis

"Semantic content is not a static symbol but a dynamical destination in state space."

In the **RPU architecture**, meaning corresponds to stable attractors, while communication consists of controlled transitions between their basins of attraction.

Concept

Classical information theory describes signal transmission but does not provide a physical representation of meaning. **Attractor-Based Semantics** introduces a dynamical interpretation:

- **Information:** A transient perturbation of the system.
- **Semantics:** A stable attractor of the dynamics.
- **Meaning:** A realized stable dynamical configuration.

Minimal Dynamical Model

Semantic states are governed by a minimal nonlinear dynamical system:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\Psi} = \left(\frac{Q}{2} - \Delta\right)\Psi - c\Psi^3 \\ \dot{Q} = \frac{1}{\tau}(K_0 + \alpha\Psi - Q) \end{cases}$$

Parameters:

- Ψ — synchronization parameter (Coherence)
- Q — adaptive control variable
- Δ — dissipation parameter | c — nonlinear saturation
- τ — relaxation time | K_0 — baseline excitation | α — coupling

Semantic States

Stationary solutions define the logical topography of the processor:

1. **Neutral State ($\Psi \approx 0$):**
Low synchronization, absence of resonance, baseline dynamics.
2. **Coherent State ($\Psi > 0$):**
Synchronized activity, stable resonance, structured dynamics.

Structural Stability & Robustness

Semantic states are inherently robust. Small perturbations do not change the final attractor:

$$x(0) + \varepsilon \in B(A_i) \Rightarrow x(t) \rightarrow A_i$$

Conclusion: Meaning is stable under noise as a direct consequence of **Lyapunov stability**.

Interpretation

Understanding corresponds to the alignment of attractor structures between different systems. **Communication** is interpreted as transitions between compatible attractors across the RPU-Fabric.

Robustness & Security: Stability from Physical Dynamics

1. Intrinsic Robustness

Unlike conventional digital processors that may become vulnerable to single-bit errors, the RPU architecture operates as a dissipative dynamical system. Computation corresponds to the relaxation of the system toward a stable attractor in phase space.

Key properties:

- **Self-Recovery:** External perturbations produce only temporary deviations from the attractor; the system autonomously returns to its functional state.
- **Physical Noise Filtering:** Dissipative dynamics and cubic saturation naturally filter weak noise and parasitic signals below the basin of attraction threshold.

2. Stability Mechanisms

The system dynamics contains built-in stabilizing mechanisms:

- **Chaos Suppression:** The cubic saturation term $-c\Psi^3$ limits amplitude growth and prevents runaway trajectories, ensuring bounded physical behavior.
- **Bounded Dynamics:** All trajectories remain confined within a finite region of phase space, forming a stable **basin of attraction** for the computational state.

3. Recovery from Perturbations

The "Recovery Dynamics" experiment demonstrates the system's ability to return to equilibrium after a strong disturbance (up to 50% simultaneous perturbation of both state variables Ψ and Q). The trajectory temporarily deviates from the attractor but subsequently relaxes back to the stable equilibrium, ensuring reliable convergence to the correct computational result.

4. Stability Analysis

System stability is rigorously proven using Lyapunov analysis: for all trajectories in the basin of attraction, the function $V(\Psi, Q)$ satisfies $\dot{V} < 0$, guaranteeing monotonic energy decay and asymptotic convergence toward the equilibrium state.

Conclusion:

The intrinsic stability of the RPU dynamical system provides natural robustness against perturbations and transient disturbances. Because computation corresponds to the relaxation toward a stable attractor, deviations caused by noise or external interference tend to decay through the system's dissipative dynamics, enhancing reliability beyond purely digital error-correction mechanisms.

Trajectory response to 50% simultaneous perturbation of state variables. The system temporarily deviates but autonomously relaxes back to stable equilibrium Ψ^* , demonstrating robust self-recovery.*

RPU Lyapunov Energy Landscape: The Path to Meaning

Visualization of $V(\Psi, Q)$ showing the global basin of attraction. All trajectories exhibit monotonic energy decay ($\dot{V} < 0$) toward the equilibrium state.

Computing Principle: Attractor Selection

1. Paradigm Shift

RPU performs computation by dynamically shaping its **Energy Landscape** $V(\Psi, Q)$. The system undergoes physical relaxation toward the configuration of minimum energy.

2. Computational Flow

- Input:** Data is mapped to control parameters (K_0, α, Δ) .
- Process:** Parameters deform the potential topology, placing the global minimum at the solution coordinate.
- Output:** The system "falls" into the attractor, yielding the result.

Verdict: The answer is not calculated; it is **selected** as the most stable physical state.

Experimental Verification: Monte-Carlo & Stability Mapping

1. Monte-Carlo Basin Analysis

To evaluate the reliability of the RPU-1 architecture, we performed a Monte-Carlo stress test on a 100x100 grid of initial conditions (10,000 simulations).

- Observation:** The system exhibits a clear **Phase Boundary** in the (Ψ_0, Q_0) space.
- Result:** The positive attractor capture rate is **32.0%** within the tested range.
- Scientific Insight:** The non-linear "cliff" observed in Fig 7.1 represents the physical limit of the basin of attraction. Beyond this boundary, the system's dissipative dynamics drive the state toward alternative equilibria, demonstrating high predictability of the computational outcome.

2. Nonlinear Filtering & Resilience

The dynamics effectively behave as a **nonlinear low-pass filter**, suppressing high-frequency stochastic perturbations. Even when the initial state is far from equilibrium, the cubic saturation term ensures the trajectory remains bounded and relaxes toward a functional state.

Fig. 7.1: Monte-Carlo Convergence Map (32.0%)

The dark blue region identifies the robust starting conditions for positive attractor capture. The sharp boundary confirms the deterministic nature of the RPU relaxation process.

RPU - 1 Full Research Suite

RPU-1: Physical Energy Minimization Landscape

Energy Minimization in High-Noise Regime ($\omega = 1$)

N	steps	time	psi	energy	converged
0	32	5000	0.33187317848205566	0.1908967242332914	False
1	32	5000	0.31284594535827637	0.08404138029269459	False
2	32	5000	0.3258185386657715	0.25057615713684867	False
3	32	5000	0.32290172576904297	0.11956064056928173	False
4	32	5000	0.31440305709838867	0.23953388580437843	False
5	32	5000	0.3734910488128662	0.07849696595876143	False
6	32	5000	0.3063089847564697	0.12684156035455746	False
7	32	5000	0.3088665008544922	0.08124608546898018	False
8	32	5000	0.3124661445617676	0.30707931643782127	False
9	32	5000	0.39446258544921875	0.1781250024113804	False
10	32	5000	0.34447193145751953	0.060573041760865455	False
11	32	5000	0.3064539432525635	0.22339272131141	False
12	32	5000	0.31813597679138184	0.10166867318616399	False
13	32	5000	0.30513739585876465	0.11955132606427332	False
14	32	5000	0.3071558475494385	0.06827836992006871	False
15	32	5000	0.3099358081817627	0.3572035496758031	False
16	32	5000	0.3067615032196045	0.06479227420185714	False
17	32	5000	0.30957794189453125	0.26223085012257447	False
18	32	5000	0.30576086044311523	0.10917846714272016	False
19	32	5000	0.3103828430175781	0.19248442587893058	False
20	64	5000	0.5858709812164307	0.07700415280228316	False
21	64	5000	0.5921776294708252	0.19550635255461796	False
22	64	5000	0.5764808654785156	0.14370735975683452	False
23	64	5000	0.5619118213653564	0.04980576982116106	False
24	64	5000	0.5615098476409912	0.1744533313793758	False
25	64	5000	0.5626790523529053	0.11485536311172256	False
26	64	5000	0.560532808303833	0.10710123741908895	False
27	64	5000	0.6079964637756348	0.06376479632133565	False
28	64	5000	0.5631582736968994	0.03334992963159109	False
29	64	5000	0.5618546009063721	0.09243112797071652	False
30	64	5000	0.560894250869751	0.04972708394521127	False
31	64	5000	0.563237190246582	0.19932025574396162	False
32	64	5000	0.7820155620574951	0.14832951753171567	False
33	64	5000	0.7201423645019531	0.12138162067185539	False
34	64	5000	0.5628211498260498	0.09637079556269802	False
35	64	5000	0.5620260238647461	0.16626927648585998	False
36	64	5000	0.5627188682556152	0.0655820815296939	False
37	64	5000	0.5625860691070557	0.07043106562092512	False
38	64	5000	0.559812068939209	0.11336737627424613	False
39	64	5000	0.5598890781402588	0.21062360114854056	False
40	128	5000	1.6799776554107666	0.05781117344002349	False
41	128	5000	1.505911111831665	0.07657567322321455	False
42	128	5000	1.505169153213501	0.0787996037998167	False
43	128	5000	1.5194923877716064	0.08172459099551205	False
44	128	5000	1.4987800121307373	0.09916100885746829	False
45	128	5000	1.498948574066162	0.12639827697335734	False
46	128	5000	1.5033268928527832	0.09126887387379502	False
47	128	5000	1.5022327899932861	0.017680399101351746	False
48	128	5000	1.539726734161377	0.0855877428420971	False
49	128	5000	1.5197227001190186	0.06999829669048709	False
50	128	5000	1.7745184898376465	0.11823158133411878	False
51	128	5000	1.5853700637817383	0.06089904017020814	False
52	128	5000	1.5022990703582764	0.10741088462035508	False
53	128	5000	1.523893117904663	0.08277317299559113	False
54	128	5000	1.5033245086669922	0.09214271459872857	False
55	128	5000	1.4994118213653564	0.03342794509944859	False
56	128	5000	1.5618386268615723	0.06934526826286574	False
57	128	5000	1.5745468139648438	0.06486579026576368	False
58	128	5000	1.5025296211242676	0.03987900022675739	False
59	128	5000	1.5132503509521484	0.06207300306569116	False
60	256	5000	7.469180583953857	0.12029011779039839	False
61	256	5000	7.077599763870239	0.07125974307512356	False
62	256	5000	7.068467617034912	0.019666622066622345	False
63	256	5000	7.404476165771484	0.021545401876013226	False
64	256	5000	7.2576329708099365	0.016067591617311337	False
65	256	5000	7.202288866043091	0.040527033868454666	False
66	256	5000	7.480191469192505	0.020348989926536144	False
67	256	5000	7.072665691375732	0.057147793673504046	False

Computational Cost: Hardware Bottleneck Analysis

RPU-1: Energy Relaxation & Spatial Entrainment

Phase landscape (ARK V7 Stable Chimera)

Phase landscape (ARK V8 Drifting Janus)

Phase landscape (ARK V8 Drifting Janus)

